

UN IRP Assessment of Resource Efficiency and Climate Change Mitigation (RECC) for G7, India, and China

Documentation of the transport-sector model within the RECC model framework

v1.0

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1 Overview

This documentation describes transport-related modeling of the RECC project (E. Hertwich et al., 2019) and supplements the main documentation (Pauliuk, 2019). While the main model documentation already covers the mathematical formulation of various parameters, here we focus on describing data assumptions, deriving data points, exchange of information with other parts (I/II/III) of the model framework, and names of parameters, e.g. `parameter_xyz`, within the database. The transport model is contained in part II of the RECC modeling framework (Figure 1) and is linked to part I, the scenario database, and part III, ODYM-RECC. Since there is no direct exchange with IV we do not describe this part of the model here.

The scenario database (I) is based on the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) database¹ which has been extended for this work. SSPs describe comprehensive scenario storylines for future human and societal development (Riahi et al., 2017). For RECC we adopt two scenarios from the SSP database: SSP1 (‘Sustainability’) is the most ambitious scenario in terms of climate change mitigation, while SSP2 (‘Middle of the Road’) follows a medium mitigation trajectory. In addition, we adopt LED, a scenario of low energy demand assuring decent living standards (Grubler et al., 2018).

The main model used for this work is ODYM-RECC (III), which describes life cycles of climate-relevant bulk materials demanded by major end-use sectors (Pauliuk & Heeren, 2019). The ODYM-RECC model is hosted on GitHub in an open repository,² while the accompanying database can be found open access on Zenodo (Pauliuk et al., 2019).

Figure 1: RECC model framework and database, overall structure. Figure drawn by Niko Heeren.

¹http://www.iiasa.ac.at/web/home/research/researchPrograms/Energy/SSP_Scenario_Database.html

²<https://github.com/YaleCIE/ODYM-RECC>

2 Vehicle archetypes

Vehicle archetypes are defined directly within the transport sector model (II). They represent typical vehicles for each size segment, technology and design. We include four size segments, six powertrain technologies, and two production designs, equating to a total of 48 archetypes (Figure 2). Segments include micro car, passenger car, minivan/sports utility vehicle (SUV), and light truck. Powertrains include internal combustion engine vehicles running on either gasoline (ICEV-g) or diesel (ICEV-d), hybrid electric vehicles (HEV), plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEV), battery electric vehicles (BEV) and hydrogen fuel cell electric vehicles (HFCEV). The two production designs are conventional and lightweight.

Figure 2: Array of vehicle archetypes across three dimensions. ICEV=internal combustion engine vehicle; HEV=hybrid electric vehicle; PHEV=plug-in hybrid electric vehicle; BEV=battery electric vehicle; HFCEV=hydrogen fuel cell electric vehicle; g=gasoline; d=diesel.

The conventional ICEV-g passenger car and light truck archetypes are modelled off of the Toyota Corolla and the Ford F-150, the highest-sold vehicles worldwide in their respective segments in 2018³. The microcar is modelled off of the Maruti Suzuki Alto, the-highest selling car in India between 2004 and 2018.⁴ The Alto has been sold 35 million times, which is comparable to the popular Volkswagen Golf.⁵ The minivan/SUV has been modelled off of the Wuling Hongguang, which is the most popular vehicle in China.⁶ Chinese sales of the Hongguang are exceeding European sales of the Golf since 2013.⁷

Several data points on performance, weight and dimensions have been collected for each of these vehicles from manufacturer homepages, and several additional sources. Table 1 shows an

³<https://www.best-selling-cars.com/global/2018-full-year-international-global-top-selling-car-models/>

⁴<https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/industry/auto/cars-uvs/maruti-suzuki-alto-crosses-35-lakh-cumulative-sales-mark/articleshow/63171749.cms>

⁵<https://www.greencarcongress.com/2013/06/wolfsburg-20130614.html>

⁶<https://www.goodwood.com/grr/road/news/2018/4/axons-automotive-anorak-chinas-best-selling-cars/>

⁷<http://carsalesbase.com>

Figure 3: Characteristics of vehicle archetypes. a) Drive-cycle energy consumption of baseline and lightweight vehicles. b) Baseline vehicle weight by component. Circles indicate total weights of lightweight vehicles. c) Material composition of baseline vehicles. d) Material composition of lightweight vehicles. Figure reproduced from Wolfram et al. (2020). ICEV=internal combustion engine vehicle; HEV=hybrid electric vehicle; PHEV=plug-in hybrid electric vehicle; BEV=battery electric vehicle; HFCEV=hydrogen fuel cell electric vehicle; g=gasoline; d=diesel; PC=passenger car; SUV=sports utility vehicle; LT=light truck.

example for the Toyota Corolla and the Ford F-150, which serve as the passenger car and light truck archetypes. When different options exist, we average their characteristics. For example, the Ford F-150 is sold as a two- and a four-wheel drive option, considerably differing in curb weight, fuel tank capacity, driving range, fuel consumption and vehicle dimensions. Since sales shares between the two options are unknown, we average between the two. The selected vehicles, powered by combustion engines, serve as the foundation for alternative powertrains. To model alternative powertrains off of ICEVs, components are added, removed or scaled as needed (Wolfram & Wiedmann, 2017). The masses of individual powertrain components are determined using variable (in kg/kW or kg/kWh) and fixed masses (in kg) compiled by Bauer et al. (2015) (Table 2). Fixed masses of vehicle body and chassis are taken from the GREET2 model (Wang, 2017; Burnham, Wang, & Wu, 2006). The resulting component and total vehicle masses are illustrated in Figure 3b. The vehicle mass breakdown by material⁸ is also based on the GREET2 model and illustrated in Figure 3c and 3d. Modifications to the original material composition from GREET2 are described in section 3.5.

PHEVs are assumed to equally operate on gasoline and electricity, i.e. their utility factor equals to 0.5. Fuel-powered cars (ICEV, HEV, HFCEV) have a utility factor of zero, whereas

⁸3_MC_VehicleArchetypes

Table 1: Exemplary vehicle characteristics of conventionally designed ICEV-g. ICEV=internal combustion engine vehicle; g=gasoline.

	Passenger car	Light truck
Curb weight	1,297	2,038
Engine power, kW	100	240
Electric motor power, kW	-	-
Fuel cell system power, kW	-	-
Nominal battery capacity, kWh	-	-
Battery power, kW	-	-
Fuel tank capacity, kWh	445	992
Electric driving range	-	-
Fuel driving range	658	938
Utility factor	0	0
Wheelbase, mm	2,700	3,633
Length, mm	4,648	5,839
Width, mm	1,778	2,029
Height, mm	1,448	1,937
Acceleration (0-97 km/h), s	8.6	6.9
Coefficient of drag	0.29	0.37

BEVs have a utility factor of one.⁹

2.1 Drive-cycle simulations

Above described vehicle characteristics are used as input data for drive-cycle simulations in FASTSim (Brooker et al., 2015), which is soft-linked to our transport model (II). Specific inputs include vehicle mass, motorization, energy storage, vehicle dimensions, and drag coefficient for each vehicle segment and powertrain (Table 1).¹⁰ Operational energy use is determined over EPA’s US06 drive cycle and is automatically corrected for real-world conditions (USEPA, 2018) by the software. According to our simulations, real-world energy consumption is roughly 30–40% higher than test-cycle energy use. For lightweighted vehicle archetypes, we assume that power components are resized for performance equivalency in accordance with the literature. Specifically, peak power is reduced incrementally until the acceleration of conventional and lightweighted vehicle archetypes match (Brooker, Ward, & Wang, 2013), while a secondary mass reduction factor of 0.5 is assumed (H. C. Kim & Wallington, 2013). Depending on segment and power train, lightweighting achieves vehicle energy use reductions by about 6–15%. The resulting operational energy use per archetype is contained in `3_EI_VehicleArchetypes` and is scaled by future total demand¹¹ in order to derive total system-wide use-phase energy demand (within III).

⁹`3_SHA_EnergyCarrierSplit_Vehicles`

¹⁰The complete dataset on vehicle characteristics is not part of the RECC database and is available at <https://github.com/PaulWolfram/MatEff.git>.

¹¹`1_F_ServiceFlows_Future`

Table 2: Variable and fixed masses of powertrain components (Bauer et al., 2015). ICEV=internal combustion engine vehicle; HEV=hybrid electric vehicle; PHEV=plug-in hybrid electric vehicle; BEV=battery electric vehicle; HFCEV=hydrogen fuel cell electric vehicle; g=gasoline; d=diesel.

	ICEV-g	ICEV-d	HEV	PHEV	BEV	HFCEV
Engine, fixed, kg	60	69	60	60		
Engine, variable, kg/kW	0.7	0.8	0.7	0.7		
Electric motor, fixed, kg			22	22	22	22
Electric motor, variable, kg/kW			0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9
Fuel cell system, fixed, kg						40
Fuel cell system, variable, kg/kW						1.1
Li-ion battery, fixed, kg			30	30	30	30
Li-ion battery, variable, kg/kWh			8.3	8.3	8.3	8.3
Fuel and tank, fixed, kg	10	10	10	10		40
Fuel and tank, variable, kg/kWh	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1		0.3
Transmission, fixed, kg	55	55	55	35	35	35
Transmission, variable, kg/kWh	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.4	0.4	0.4

2.2 Service demand and type split

Historic and future transport service demand¹² are defined in the scenario database (I) of the RECC model framework. Historic demand per region is informed by a range of national statistics and reports^{13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22} and peer-reviewed literature (Goel, Mohan, Guttikunda, & Tiwari, 2016; Huo, Zhang, He, Yao, & Wang, 2012; Hao, Wang, Ouyang, & Cheng, 2011; Darido, Torres-Montoya, & Mehndiratta, 2014), and is summarized in Table 3.

Future demand is given exogenously as a function of population and per-capita demand levels. Future population data²³ is based on the SSP database, while transport demand develops as shown in Table 4.²⁴ Vehicle ownership levels converge to 0.47 vehicles/person in LED, and to 0.5 in SSP1, while for SSP2 it is assumed that vehicle ownership remains constant but at least 0.5 in the global North, while the global South catches up to 0.5 vehicles/capita. Based on the main text and Supporting Tables 15 and 16 in Grubler et al. (2018) we estimate that

¹²1_F_ServiceFlows_Future

¹³<https://crashstats.nhtsa.dot.gov/Api/Public/ViewPublication/809952>

¹⁴<https://www.statista.com/statistics/738667/us-vehicles-projected-age/>

¹⁵<https://www.statista.com/statistics/680051/japan-passenger-car-average-age/>

¹⁶<https://www.statista.com/statistics/314719/average-car-and-van-occupancy-in-england/>

¹⁷<https://www.statista.com/statistics/865046/china-passenger-vehicles-average-age/>

¹⁸<https://www.energy.gov/eere/vehicles/fact-613-march-8-2010-vehicle-occupancy-rates>

¹⁹<http://oee.nrcan.gc.ca/publications/statistics/cvs05/pdf/cvs05.pdf>

²⁰<http://www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/efficiency-by-sector/transport/distance-travelled-by-car.html>

²¹<https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators/occupancy-rates-of-passenger-vehicles/occupancy-rates-of-passenger-vehicles>

²²<https://www.acea.be/statistics/tag/category/average-vehicle-age>

²³2_P_RECC_Population_SSP_32R

²⁴1_F_ServiceFlows_Future

the vehicle occupancy rises to about 2.9 in the global North and to about 3.4 in the global South by 2050,²⁵ while annual vehicle mileage converges to a level of roughly 8,500–8,800 km per year.²⁶ In SSP2 we allow for modest growth in vehicle mileage, and constant occupancy factors unless carsharing is implemented as an ME strategy (see next section). SSP1 assumes a moderate reduction in vehicle mileage and a constant vehicle occupancy unless carsharing is implemented.

Service demand is then split by powertrain types²⁷ following IEA’s Energy Technology Perspectives (see Figure 7.16 therein). The baseline scenario describes continued strong growth of ICEVs and a moderate growth of hybrids. Blue Map describes a rapid shift away from ICEVs towards alternative powertrains. For RECC, IEA’s baseline scenario is assumed to match SSP2, while Blue Map is assumed to match LED and SSP1. Within RECC–ODYM (III) different parameters translate service demand into vehicle stocks, i.e. the number of existing vehicles on the road.²⁸ For further information please refer to the main model documentation (Pauliuk, 2019), especially equations 17–20 therein.

Table 3: Estimated population, car ownership, transport demand and vehicle occupancy by region for the baseline year 2015. vkm=vehicle kilometers.

Region	Population (mio.)	Cars/ person	pkm/ year	Persons/ car
USA	326	0.67	22,508	1.60
Japan	127	0.48	6,736	1.50
Canada	36	0.61	15,887	1.62
UK	65	0.47	9,571	1.55
France	64	0.44	8,636	1.50
Germany	82	0.52	10,438	1.42
Italy	60	0.61	8,454	1.45
China	1,370	0.10	2,049	1.26
India	1,309	0.02	334	1.50

Table 4: Development of annual transport demand (pkm/year) in three scenarios.

Scenario	USA	JP	CAN	UK	FRA	GER	IT	CHN	IN
2015	22,508	6,736	15,887	9,571	8,636	10,438	8,454	2,049	334
2050 (LED)	8,800	8,434	9,000	8,434	8,434	8,834	8,434	4,000	1,350
2050 (SSP1)	17,000	8,434	13,100	10,212	9,748	9,748	8,434	10,010	8,700
2050 (SSP2)	22,508	8,434	15,887	10,212	9,748	9,748	8,454	10,010	8,700

²⁵6_MIP_VehicleOccupancyRate

²⁶3_IO_Vehicles_UsePhase

²⁷3_SHA_TypeSplit_Vehicles

²⁸2_S_RECC_FinalProducts_2015_passvehicles

3 Description of ME strategies

ME strategies are broadly defined as a set of technical measures and/or policy interventions that can lead to a significant reduction in the use of energy-intensive materials (Allwood, Ashby, Gutowski, & Worrell, 2011; E. G. Hertwich et al., 2019). ME strategies are defined within the scenario database (I) and passed on to the transport sector model (II). Here we describe assumptions and derivation of the relevant parameters. Mathematical descriptions can be found in the main documentation (Pauliuk, 2019). A summary of all strategies can also be found in Table 10 in E. Hertwich et al. (2019). It is worth mentioning that many of the strategies are represented in a broad-brush manner by changing aggregate parameters such as recycling rates.

3.1 Carsharing (CaS)

While the definition of carsharing is not clear-cut it can be described as a shift away from the personal car to the use of cars from a shared fleet. Most commonly, three different forms of carsharing are distinguished: free-floating (e.g. Car2Go, DriveNow), stationary (e.g. Zipcar) and peer-to-peer car sharing (e.g. Getaround). While stationary carshare programs refer to round-trips, free-floating carsharing gives members the flexibility of driving a vehicle from A to B without having to return the vehicle. Peer-to-peer carsharing is a model where existing vehicle owners lend their car to other peers for a short period of time.

Sperling and Shaheen (1999) estimate that carsharing members reduce their driving by 30–60%. Martin and Shaheen (2016) found through a North American survey that the average driving per respondents decreased by 27% after joining carsharing (from 6,468 km/year to 4,729 km/year). In a nationwide study, Martin et al. (2010) conducted an online survey of North American carsharing members that use the neighborhood business model, a form of peer-to-peer carsharing at the neighborhood level. From the 6,281 households that responded, 2,968 households owned a car, translating to 0.47 vehicles per household. After switching to car sharing, the sample owned 1,507 vehicles, about 0.24 vehicles per household. Car ownership was roughly halved. At city level the authors found that each shared vehicle replaced between 1 to 11 private vehicles in five major Northern American cities (Martin & Shaheen, 2016). Every Zipcar is reported to take 13 private vehicles off the road.²⁹

Accordingly here we assume that a complete adoption of carsharing would half car ownership³⁰ which, as a consequence, would cut driven vehicle kilometers in half. The adoption of carsharing however is limited here to about 30% of total transport demand (pkm/year) in LED, and to 25% in SSP1 and 15% in SSP1 in all regions.³¹ Please refer to equations 4–14 in the main model documentation (Pauliuk, 2019) for a detailed mathematical formulation.

3.2 Ridesharing (RiS)

Ridesharing refers to a situation in which individuals with matching itineraries and time schedules share a private vehicle and split travel costs (gas, tolls, parking fees . . .) to perform their trips (Furuhata et al., 2013). Ridesharing is not to be confused with ride-hailing, an app-based

²⁹<https://www.zipcar.com/carsharing>

³⁰6_MIP_CarSharing_Stock

³¹6_PR_CarSharingShare

service to arrange an on-demand ride in a usually privately owned vehicle (for example UBER or Lyft).³² Based on an integrated transport land-use model, Yin et al. (2018) have found that ridesharing could lead to a 25–75% increase in vehicle occupancy in the Paris region. In this work we assume that a complete adoption of ridesharing could increase occupancy factors by 40%.³³ The adoption of ridesharing however is limited here to about 30% of total transport demand (pkm/year) in LED, and to 25% in SSP1 and 15% in SSP1 in all regions.³⁴ Ridesharing is also assumed in the LED scenario. We infer the respective occupancy factors from the main text and Supplementary Tables 15 and 16 in Grubler et al. (2018). Please refer to equations 4–14 in the main model documentation (Pauliuk, 2019) for details on the mathematical formulation.

Table 5: Baseline vehicle occupancy (persons/vehicle) in 2015 and by region and scenario.

Scenario	USA	JP	CAN	UK	FRA	GER	IT	CHN	IN
2015	1.60	1.50	1.62	1.55	1.50	1.42	1.45	1.26	1.50
2050 (LED)	2.27	2.13	2.30	2.20	2.13	2.02	2.06	1.79	2.13
2050 (SSP1)	2.16	2.03	2.19	2.09	2.03	1.92	1.96	1.70	2.03
2050 (SSP2)	1.94	1.82	1.96	1.88	1.82	1.72	1.75	1.52	1.82

3.3 Lifetime extension (LTE)

The lifetime of new and existing products can be prolonged, due to more robust design that allows for easier exchange for parts that wear down quicker than the structural components, or that change more rapidly than the latter due to changes in consumer preference (fashion) or safety standards. Here we assume a 20% lifetime extension for PHEVs, BEVs, and HFCEVs, but not for ICEV-g, ICEV-d, and HEVs.³⁵ The reason therefore is that a longer lifetime of ICEVs and HEVs would not lead to an overall emissions reduction as it would delay the introduction of electric vehicles and would therefore not be in line with the goals of this work. For more information please refer to the main report, especially to equation 16 therein.

The gradual implementation of the lifetime extension potential is simulated by multiplying the maximum potential with a scale-up curve,³⁶ which quantifies the extent to which a given industry material efficiency strategy will be implemented. This curve applies to the material efficiency strategy parameters EoL, FYI, FSD and LTE and is dependent on time, region, socio-economic scenario, and climate policy scenario. In the current implementation (ODYM-RECC v2.2), a linear increase of the scale-up curve from 0% in 2019 to 100% in 2040 is assumed, followed by a spline interpolation to reduce the changes in the first derivative.

³²<http://blog.liftshare.com/liftshare/carsharing-carpooling-ridesharing-whats-the-difference>

³³6_MIP_RideSharing_Occupancy

³⁴6_PR_RideSharingShare

³⁵6_PR_LifeTimeExtension_passvehicles

³⁶3_SHA_RECC_REStrategyScaleUp

3.4 Using less by design (ULD)

Transitioning from larger to smaller vehicles reduces materials used in vehicle construction and can therefore reduce the energy and carbon embodied in the vehicle stock. One can shift from larger, heavier to smaller, lighter vehicles within a vehicle segment, but such shifts are not represented here. Instead, we represent a size reduction by a shift towards lighter vehicle segments. Possible transition pathways include light truck→van/SUV, van/SUV→passenger car, passenger car→micro car. No further size reduction of micro cars is implemented. As a baseline, we assume that the current vehicle type split stays constant. ULD can reduce vehicle weight by 16–44% and fuel consumption by 9–37%, depending on vehicle segment and powertrain (Figure 3).

ULD is implemented as an increasing share of smaller vehicles as a fraction of new vehicle registrations and differs by region, vehicle type, and socio-economic scenario.³⁷ For more information refer to the ODYM-RECC model documentation, especially equations 21 and 22 therein.

3.5 Material substitution (MSu)

Substituting steel with lightweight materials, such as aluminum, can lead to vehicle weight reduction and hence improve the fuel economy of vehicles. However, this often entails increasing emissions from vehicle production (H. C. Kim & Wallington, 2013). Yet, higher production impacts can be mediated by powertrain resizing for performance equivalency (H. C. Kim & Wallington, 2013) and by deploying secondary (recycled) lightweighting materials (H.-J. Kim, McMillan, Keoleian, & Skerlos, 2010). We define one conventional and one lightweighting material mix, largely based on the GREET2 model (Wang, 2017). The only difference in our lightweighting material mix is that we substitute carbon-fiber (CFRP) and glass-fiber composites (GFRP) with aluminum due to recyclability issues that occur with fibers.³⁸ Here we increase the content of aluminum by 10–28% and reduce steel content by 25–31%, depending on powertrain (cf. Figure 3 and Table 6).

The procedure of replacing carbon fiber with aluminum is as follows:

1. Estimate material replacement coefficients (MRC) for several materials (Table 7). MRC values are adjusted such that the difference between the calculated mass reduction of steel and the default value from GREET2 is minimized by using the Solver tool in Microsoft Excel[®]. The mass of materials is reported at the vehicle component level (e.g. mass of steel in the vehicle body), while material replacement for lightweighting is reported at the level of vehicle parts (sub-components) level. This difference in resolution imposes a challenge for mapping material replacement to the change of mass of individual materials because multiple replacement pathways exist (e.g., ‘steel replaced by wrought Al’, ‘steel replaced by Mg’, ‘steel replaced by carbon fiber’). Therefore, it is important to estimate the MRC for each individual material for such a ‘one-to-many’ mapping problem.
2. Calculate the amount of steel replaced by CFRP/GFRP using the MRCs determined in

³⁷3_SHA_DownSizing_Vehicles

³⁸<https://www.compositesworld.com/blog/post/the-state-of-recycled-carbon-fiber>

Table 6: Material composition of conventional and lightweighted vehicle archetypes. Data sources: (Wang, 2017; Burnham et al., 2006). ICEV=internal combustion engine vehicle; HEV=hybrid electric vehicle; PHEV=plug-in hybrid electric vehicle; BEV=battery electric vehicle; HFCEV=hydrogen fuel cell electric vehicle; g=gasoline; d=diesel.

	Autom. steel	Stainl. steel	Cast iron	Wrought Al	Cast Al	Copper, el. grade	Plastics	Other
Conventional								
ICEV-g	0.62	0.00	0.10	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.11	0.08
ICEV-d	0.62	0.00	0.10	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.11	0.08
HEV	0.64	0.00	0.07	0.01	0.06	0.04	0.11	0.07
PHEV	0.59	0.00	0.07	0.03	0.06	0.05	0.02	0.18
BEV	0.57	0.00	0.02	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.10	0.16
HFCEV	0.57	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.12	0.17
Lightweight								
ICEV-g	0.31	0.01	0.04	0.23	0.17	0.03	0.13	0.08
ICEV-d	0.31	0.01	0.04	0.23	0.17	0.03	0.13	0.08
HEV	0.34	0.01	0.04	0.21	0.17	0.05	0.12	0.07
PHEV	0.31	0.01	0.03	0.20	0.16	0.06	0.11	0.12
BEV	0.19	0.00	0.03	0.25	0.17	0.08	0.13	0.15
HFCEV	0.22	0.02	0.03	0.30	0.18	0.05	0.14	0.05

step 1. The total mass of steel that could be replaced by different lightweight materials is calculated using Equation 1.

3. Calculate the amount of Al needed to replace the same amount of steel determined in step 2.
4. Set the value of CFRP/GFRP to zero and add the amount of Al calculated from step 3 to the corresponding rows.

$$M_{steel-reduction} = \sum_{m=1}^n \frac{M_{LW}^m - M_{BL}^m}{MRC_{m,j}} \quad (1)$$

where

- $M_{steel-reduction}$ is the total mass of steel that is avoided by using n types of lightweight materials m , in kg
- M_{LW}^m is the mass of lightweight material m used in the lightweight vehicle, in kg
- M_{BL}^m is the mass of lightweight material m used in the baseline vehicle, in kg
- $MRC_{m,j}$ is the material replacement coefficient for lightweight material m to replace steel in component j (fraction)

Table 7: Material replacement coefficients (MRCs) of replacing steel with lightweighting materials in the vehicle body and chassis. CFRP=carbon fiber reinforced polymer; GFRP=glass fiber reinforced polymer; Al=aluminum; Mg=magnesium.

From material x to y	Body	Chassis
Steel → CFRP	0.59	
Steel → GFRP		0.51
Steel → Cast Al		0.62
Steel → Wrought Al	0.69	
Steel → Mg	0.60	

Additional (secondary) weight reduction can be achieved through downsizing of components, which is a consequence of primary weight savings by material substitution. For the powertrain, we adopt the assumption of an an additional 50% secondary weight reduction (H. C. Kim & Wallington, 2013; Das, 2011). The relative material composition is identical for different size segments of the same powertrain. Depending on the power train, lightweighting can reduce vehicle weight by 18–24%. These findings are consistent with Bandivadekar et al. (2008), who find that about a 20% vehicle weight reduction is possible with aggressive material substitution. Secondary weight reduction is particularly high for BEVs due to the high initial weight of the large battery. This finding is also confirmed by Hofer et al. (2014). The fuel consumption of both the baseline and lightweighted vehicle options are simulated in FASTSim (section 2.1).

The market share of lightweighted vehicles for each powertrain follows an implementation curve.³⁹ According to this curve, the share of lightweighted vehicles in LED and SSP1 grows from about 12% to 75% by 2050, and then remains at that level, while in SSP2 the share grows linearly to 62% by 2100. Currently, the mass of aluminum is about 12% as a share of the total weight of an average US passenger car.^{40,41,42} Since aluminum is the main lightweighting material in this work we use this value as a proxy for the share of lightweighted vehicles as a fraction of all vehicles. For each powertrain, the total number of lightweighted vehicles can be obtained by multiplying this market share value with the inflow of corresponding vehicles in a given year for exchange with the ODYM model (III). The weighted material composition for each powertrain for a given year is then determined as the weighted average material composition, based on the number of conventional and lightweighted vehicles. For more information refer to the main model documentation, especially equations 21 and 22 therein.

³⁹3_SHA_LightWeighting_Vehicles

⁴⁰<https://cta.ornl.gov/data/chapter3.shtml>

⁴¹<https://cta.ornl.gov/data/chapter4.shtml>

⁴²<https://cta.ornl.gov/data/chapter7.shtml>

3.6 Reuse (ReU)

Remanufacturing and reuse⁴³ of specific parts, such as engines, batteries and tires, requires the recovery of these components from end-of-life vehicles, disassembling, cleaning, repairing (if needed) and reassembling. This process can lead to considerable energy and carbon savings compared to newly manufactured components. [Sutherland et al. \(2008\)](#) find that reusing a large diesel engine could save about 90% of energy use, requiring 1,850 MJ instead of 18,100 MJ. [Z.-C. Liu et al. \(2013\)](#) find that reuse can reduce the global warming potential of a diesel engine by 69%. However, reused components may not benefit from efficiency improvements in the same way as new ones do, if at all, causing a trade-off between savings in embodied energy and higher use-phase energy needs ([Sutherland et al., 2008](#)).

Reuse rates (`6_PR_ReUse_Veh`, Table 8) have been estimated by using the following approach: First, typical reuse rates for components of Japanese vehicles have been retrieved from [Nakamura et al. \(2012\)](#). These were then mapped to the vehicle material composition of vehicle components from the GREET model ([Wang, 2017](#); [Burnham et al., 2006](#)). The resulting reuse rates were further adjusted by different vehicle lifetime mileages in different regions of the world. Specifically, while Japanese light vehicles have a typical lifetime of about 79,300 km, lifetime mileages differ by country. The adjustment is based on the premise that a longer vehicle lifetime is correlated with a lower reuse rate (equation 2):

$$r_{other,j} = r_{JP,j} \times \frac{VKT_{JP}}{VKT_{other}} \quad (2)$$

where

- $r_{other,j}$ is the reuse rate of vehicle component j in a country other than Japan
- $r_{JP,j}$ is the reuse rate of vehicle component j in Japan
- VKT_{JP} is the lifetime mileage of a vehicle in Japan, in km
- VKT_{other} is the lifetime mileage of a vehicle in a country other than Japan, in km

Table 8: Comparison of estimated current (2015) reuse rates of an ICEV-g in the US and Japan. VKT=vehicle-km travelled. ICEV=internal combustion engine vehicle; g=gasoline.

Material	US (VKT: 244,845)	Japan (VKT: 79,329)
Automotive steel	0.08	0.25
Cast iron	0.12	0.38
Cast Al	0.13	0.42
Wrought Al	0.11	0.35
Copper	0.10	0.30
Plastics	0.09	0.26

⁴³Since remanufacturing and reuse are not clearly distinguished in the literature we use the term ‘reuse’ to refer to both reuse and remanufacturing collectively. For example, note the similarity between [Nakamura et al.](#)’s definition of reuse and [Sutherland, Adler, Haapala, and Kumar](#)’s definition of remanufacturing.

To conform to the structure of ODYM–RECC, which reads material composition data at the vehicle level, and not at the component level, we translate the share of reused materials per component to the share of reused materials per vehicle using equation 3:

$$\phi_{ReU,m,g} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (M_{m,j}^{tot}) \times r_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n M_{m,j}^{tot}} \quad (3)$$

where

- $\phi_{ReU,m,g}$ is the share of material m that can be reused in the entire vehicle g , in %
- $M_{m,j}^{tot}$ is the total mass of material m in vehicle component j , in kg
- r_j is the reuse rate of vehicle component j , in %

The future share of reused components is assumed to increase in all regions following a scale-up curve⁴⁴ which converges to Japan’s 2015 level (Table 8) by 2050 in the LED and SSP1 scenarios. SSP2 is assumed to reach about half of that value. For more details please refer to the main model documentation, especially equations 28–29.

3.7 End-of-life recovery rate improvement (EoL)

Recycling of end-of-life (EoL) vehicles is quite common in many countries around the world (Sakai et al., 2014) but recovered materials often are not functionally recycled, meaning that they are used for lower-quality applications, such as construction. However, here we use generic recycling rates that apply to materials overall, rather than to specific applications, such as cars, buildings or soda cans. The current⁴⁵ and future⁴⁶ recycling rates (credits) summarized in Table 9 therefore equally apply to both cars and buildings (except for automotive steel). The emission reductions occurring from improved recycling efforts in each sector are accounted for directly in that sector.

The improvement of recycling rates follows the same scale-up curve as other industry-based material efficiency strategies (FYI, FSD) and product lifetime extension (LTE).⁴⁷ As mentioned earlier, in the current implementation (ODYM-RECC v2.2), a linear increase of the scale-up curve from 0% in 2019 to 100% in 2040 is assumed, followed by a spline interpolation to reduce the changes in the first derivative. This curve is applied to all regions and climate policy scenarios. For more details please refer to the main model documentation, especially equations 28 and 29.

3.8 Fabrication yield improvement (FYI)

Fabrication yield improvements (FYI) reduces the amount of material scrap in the fabrication and manufacturing process, thereby lessening the demand for material input to the manufacturing sector. Assumed current⁴⁸ and future⁴⁹ yields are shown in Table 10.

⁴⁴6_PR_ReUse_Veh

⁴⁵4_PY_EoL_RecoveryRate

⁴⁶6_PR_EoL_RR_Improvement

⁴⁷3_SHA_RECC_REStrategyScaleUp

⁴⁸4_PY_Manufacturing

⁴⁹6_PR_FabricationYieldImprovement

Table 9: Global improvement of end-of-life recycling rates in all scenarios.

Material	Current	Source	Future	Source
Automotive steel	0.69	WorldSteel (2010)	0.95	Cullen et al. (2012)
Cast iron	0.93	Cullen et al. (2012)	0.95	WorldSteel (2010)
Cast Al	0.875	G. Liu et al. (2013)	0.955	Assumption
Wrought Al	0.875	See above	0.955	Assumption
Copper	0.67	Glöser et al. (2013)	0.82	Assumption
Plastics	0.18	Zheng and Suh (2019)	0.70	Informed by discussions with an industry insider

The improvement of recycling rates follows the same scale-up curve as other industry-based material efficiency strategies (EoL, FSD) and product lifetime extension (LTE).⁵⁰ As mentioned earlier, in the current implementation (ODYM-RECC v2.2), a linear increase of the scale-up curve from 0% in 2019 to 100% in 2040 is assumed, followed by a spline interpolation to reduce the changes in the first derivative. This curve is applied to all regions and climate policy scenarios. For more details please refer to the main model documentation, especially equation 32.

Table 10: Global improvement of fabrication yield in all scenarios.

Material	Current	Source	Future	Source
Automotive steel	0.20	Pauliuk et al. (2013); Milford et al. (2013)	0.30	Pauliuk et al. (2013); Milford et al. (2013)
Stainless steel	0.20	See above	0.30	See above
Cast iron	0.01	Assumption	0.01	Assumption
Cast Al	0.16	G. Liu et al. (2013)	0.16	Assumption
Wrought Al	0.16	See above	0.16	Assumption
Copper	0.33	Glöser et al. (2013)	0.33	Assumption
Plastics	0.01	Assumption	0.01	Assumption

3.9 Fabrication scrap diversion (FSD)

Here we assume that up to 80% of fabrication scrap (Milford et al., 2013)⁵¹ is diverted into other manufacturing sectors instead of being remelted.

The improvement of recycling rates follows the same scale-up curve as FYI, EoL and LTE.⁵² As mentioned earlier, in the current implementation (ODYM-RECC v2.2), a linear

⁵⁰3_SHA_RECC_REStrategyScaleUp

⁵¹6_PR_FabricationScrapDiversion

⁵²3_SHA_RECC_REStrategyScaleUp

increase of the scale-up curve from 0% in 2019 to 100% in 2040 is assumed, followed by a spline interpolation to reduce the changes in the first derivative. This curve is applied to all regions and climate policy scenarios. For more details please refer to the main model documentation, especially equation 32.

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